

“METROLOGICAL SUPPORT IN PRODUCTION AND ITS SECTORS”

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Abstract: Metrological supply in production and its branches is one of the important topics that require ensuring the quality of delivery and accurate calculations. Metrology is concerned with the identification and verification of measurements and indicators as its main objective, giving them reliable responsibility and establishing rules and standards for their use.

Metrology is critical at every stage of production, helping to ensure high levels of accuracy and reliability in quality assurance, delivery processes.

Key Words: accountability, minimize, processes, laboratory, measurement

Metrological maintenance includes the calibration of measuring instruments in every part of the production, ensuring that they work correctly and get the right results. One of the important parts of metrological supply includes calibration laboratories and standards. Calibration laboratories perform proprietary processes to verify and adjust measuring instruments for proper operation. Their composition will consist of laboratories working on the basis of private metrological tools, calibration processes and calibration standards, implementing temporary ones.

Part of the metrological supply is the setting of standards. Standards are a set of rules and requirements for measuring instruments. Their designation is intended to ensure the correct operation of measuring instruments and to ensure reliable and accurate determinations through the results obtained from them. These standards are drawn up by private metrological organizations and certificates are issued for their compliance. Metrological assurance is also important in business, helping to ensure adherence to standards, proper implementation of calibration and inspection processes, quality and accuracy, and reliable accountability for delivery to

customers. These processes are important parts of quality improvement and development of technologies in the field of production.

Metrological support in production and its branches, that is, tracking and control, including direct indication, measurement of quantities and minimization of errors in the field of products and services is a project. Metrology is concerned with the provision of measurements and quantities and the regulation of errors in them. This is an important part of ensuring the quality of products produced in industry, technology, laboratory and other areas.

Metrological supply in the production process includes the following main directions:

1. Development of measurement methods: Metrological supply includes the development of measurement methods and the development of new measurement tools. It helps to improve the quality of the industry by developing new technologies and high-quality measuring instruments.
2. Provision of standards in metrological fields: Metrological provision is engaged in the development, dissemination and provision of standards in metrological fields. Standards provide information for quality assurance and help to accurately indicate how products are measured.
3. Organization of metrological laboratories: Metrological supply, measurement and organization of metrological laboratories allow measurement and certification of standards. It helps in laboratories, product quality control, dimensioning and error detection.
4. Selection and correction of errors: Metrological maintenance is the main part of the detection and correction of errors that occur in measurement methods. This helps to understand the basis of errors and their consequences and defines a step towards quality improvement.

5. Metrological calibration: Metrological maintenance involves the calibration process to ensure the correct operation of measuring instruments. This includes the correct adjustment of measuring instruments and the detection of errors in them.

Aims to improve quality in metrological supply, industry, laboratory and technology. This process helps ensure quality and minimize errors in production lines.

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